

LINGUOCOGNITIVE FOUNDATIONS OF FILM DISCOURSE

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Abstract: This article analyzes the concept of film discourse and its linguocognitive properties. It sheds light on the scientific basis on how film discourse is formed through language, thought, and multimodal expression, as well as its relationship with cognitive frames, concepts, scenarios, and emotional reactions. During the analysis, it is explained how language units are processed in the human mind, and what semantic fields are formed through film characters and events, based on examples.

Keywords: film discourse, linguistic cognitive, frame, concept, multimodal discourse, speech act, semantic field.

The formation of new approaches in linguistics and the development of the scientific paradigm determined the need for a deep analysis of linguistic phenomena, including such concepts as "text" and "discourse". If in the first half of the 20th century the main attention of researchers was primarily focused on the structural features of language, then from the second half of the century there was a shift in attention to the functioning of language in real communicative conditions.

In the field of modern linguistics, discourse analysis has become one of the most comprehensive methodologies. In particular, the profound influence of cinema on the thinking of society, the semantic layering of its language tools, has made it an independent object of analysis. Unlike ordinary text, film discourse has multimodal, interactive and connotative properties, in which, along with language, visual, auditory and emotional components are combined. Therefore, its study based on a linguocognitive approach is one of the current scientific issues.

The concept of film discourse and its characteristics

Cinematic discourse is a type of discourse inherent in the art of cinema, inextricably linked with other non-linguistic signs (image, facial expressions, musical background, montage). It constitutes a communicative process between the screenwriter, director, actor and viewer. Scholars such as VN Toporov, TA van Dijk, ND Arutyunova, MM Bakhtin consider discourse not limited to

language alone, but as a contextual and socio-pragmatic system.¹The main features of this discourse are:

Multimodal character - through cinema, meaning is created not only through language, but also through facial expressions, gestures, visual images, background music, and other semiotic means.

Interactivity – the viewer perceives the film not passively, but cognitively actively: he understands the context, guesses the intentions of the characters, and responds emotionally.

Cognitive scripts - in film, reality is often depicted based on a stereotypical chain of events (scripts), which are associated with pre-existing knowledge and assumptions in human thinking.

Linguistic features

The linguistic elements in film discourse are specially selected. These elements are distinguished by the following aspects:

Dialogues are similar to real-life speech, but perform a more dramatic function. Each line reflects the character's psychological state, social status, and personality.

Speech acts – in film discourse, directive (command, request), expressive (emotional), and informative acts often prevail.

Pragmatic devices – context-dependent meanings, irony, metaphor, and other pragmatic indicators are widely used.

Cognitive aspects

Cognitive linguistics analyzes how film text is perceived in the human mind. The main concepts in this are:

A frame is a mental schema for understanding a real event. For example, a "war frame" or a "family frame."

A script is a stereotypical model of a sequence of events. In cinema, a script not only shapes the plot, but also cognitive expectations.

Also, emotional cognition - that is, the emotional states (fear, joy, disgust) that arise during the process of watching a film - shapes cognitive reality.

Concepts – through the characters of the film, certain concepts (for example, "freedom", "justice", "homeland") are manifested and activated in the mind of the viewer.

Emotional cognition - emotions are not only expressed through film discourse, but also evoke certain cognitive reactions in the viewer.

Analysis with examples

¹ Arutyunova, N.D. (1990). Discourse. V sb. Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary. Moscow: Soviet Encyclopedia

For example, in the famous Uzbek film "Mahallada duv-duv gap", one of the main characters' feelings is: "Don't let the story get out to the neighborhood, there's something called reputation!"

Analysis: sociocognitive elements: the phrase "talk" - metaphorical meaning: talk is cognitively interpreted as something that is physically transmitted.

Cultural code: Reputation is a mental construct, meaning it is not a real object, but it has a very strong real impact on people.

Collective discourse: The film depicts the neighborhood as a unit of social consciousness.

Multimodality and semiotic systems

To fully understand film discourse, it is important to analyze it from a multimodal perspective. Language is the primary, but not the only, tool. The following also create semantic meaning:

Visual codes (colors, composition, clothing);

Audial codes (background music, sound effects);

Cinema paradigm (film genre, cultural context).

For example, dark colors, slow movement, and soft music evoke a sense of danger or tragedy in the cognitive mind. The film analyzes national mentality, cultural values, and visible and invisible processes in the mind.

Cinematic discourse, while being a linguistic tool, is also a screened form of human thought.

Film discourse analysis combines linguistic and cognitive approaches to uncover the deep essence of film text. It reveals the inextricable link between human thought, cultural experience, and linguistic means. In today's era of globalization, studying the relationship between language and thought through film discourse is an important direction for modern linguistic research.

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